

Complete ^{13}C and ^1H Spectral Assignments of Friedelin by INADEQUATE and Heteronuclear (^{13}C - ^1H) Correlation Experiments

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Complete carbon-13 and proton spectral analyses of friedelin have been made using INADEQUATE (or CCCP) and heteronuclear (^{13}C - ^1H) correlation experiments.

DESPITE the wide-spread distribution of friedelanes in nature^{1,2} systematic analyses of their carbon spectra started only recently in contrast to other groups of triterpenoids³. Carbon spectral assignments reported for friedelin (1) itself were not only quite inconsistent along with those of other friedelanes⁴ but also it differed significantly from those calculated for 1 previously⁵ and thus these assignments required revision⁶. Subsequently a few more publications in the series came out in the literature and in many cases the assignments were inconsistent/incomplete, or were not carried out. These were reconsidered in course of our report on carbon chemical shift assignments of some natural friedelanes and transformation products thereof⁷. The recent advent of more sophisticated and quite powerful two-dimensional nmr experiments⁸ like X-H correlation⁹ and INADEQUATE¹⁰ techniques which give thorough insight into spectral problems prompted us to apply the same for complete spectral (^{13}C and ^1H) assignments of friedelin (1) which were otherwise difficult and not straightforward.

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The INADEQUATE is based on detection of natural ^{13}C - ^{13}C coupled spin systems through the creation of double quantum coherence and allows carbon-carbon connectivity mapping. The contour plot of such an experiment on 1 (Fig. 1) shows a single correlation spot vertically below the methyl carbon signal at δ 6.7 in conformity with its attachment and spin-coupling with only one adjacent carbon atom. The X-H correlation experiment (*vide infra*) further relates this carbon signal with C-23. Towards the left of the correlation spot below δ 6.7 resonance and symmetric from the diagonal there is another correlation spot below the signal at δ 58.0 (CH) indicating that they are spin-coupled and thus directly linked with. The methine carbon resonating at δ 58.0 which is related to C-4 (*vide infra* the X-H correlation experiment) shows only two correlation spots below for coupling with signals at δ 6.7 (CH_3) and 42.0 ($-\text{C}-$). The third

correlation spot expected for coupling with carbonyl carbon is not visible because of smaller spectral width employed. The non-protonated carbon resonance at δ 42.0 for C-5 is further spin-coupled to methine carbon resonance at δ 59.3 (thus assignable to C-10), methylene carbon resonance at δ 41.1 (related to C-6) and a methyl resonance at δ 14.5 (associated with C-24). The methine carbon signal at δ 59.3 (C-10) is again showing correlations with the methylene carbon signal at δ 22.1 (C-1) and a quaternary carbon resonance at δ 37.3 (C-9). The δ 22.1 methylene carbon resonance is found to be coupled with the methylene carbon signal at δ 41.4 (C-2) which should be coupled with the carbonyl carbon (again not visible in Fig. 1 for shorter spectral width employed).

The carbon network for the remaining part of the molecule could be constructed in an analogous

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Fig. 1

fashion from inspection of the INADEQUATE spectrum. The methylene carbon resonance at δ 18.0 (C-7) shows correlations with the methylene carbon signal at δ 41.1 (C-6) as well as with the methine carbon signal at δ 52.9 (C-8). This methine carbon is observed to have direct linkage with the quaternary carbons resonating at δ 37.3 and 38.1. The former signal is assigned to C-9 for it is spin-coupled to methine carbon resonance at δ 59.3 (assigned previously to C-10) and the methylene carbon resonance at δ 35.5 (C-11) as well as to methyl carbon resonance at δ 17.8 for C-25. These carbon signals accounted for rings A and B of friedelin (1) along with the methyl groups connected with (structure 1).

The methylene carbon resonance at δ 30.3 is assignable to C-12 since it is found to couple with the methylene carbon resonance at δ 35.5 (C-11) as well as with a non-protonated carbon resonance at δ 39.5 (C-13) which is further interacting with the

quaternary carbon resonance at δ 38.1 (assignable to C-14), methine carbon resonance at δ 42.6 (C-18) and the methyl resonance at δ 18.5 (C-27). The quaternary carbon signal at δ 38.1 (C-14) is directly linked with a methine carbon resonating at δ 52.9 (C-8), methylene carbon resonance at δ 32.3 (C-15) and the methyl resonance at δ 20.1 (C-26). The methylene carbon signal at δ 32.3 is found to couple further with the methylene carbon resonance at δ 35.9 for C-16 which is coupled with a quaternary carbon signal at δ 29.8 (C-17). This quaternary carbon signal is further coupled with the methine carbon resonance at δ 42.6 assigned to C-18, methylene carbon resonance at δ 39.1 (C-22) and the methyl resonance at δ 32.0 (C-28). This completed carbon signal connectivities thus exhibited for ring C and D of friedelin (1) and also the methyl groups connected with these rings (structure 1).

Again, the methine carbon resonance at δ 42.6 for C-18 is showing correlations with the methylene

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7. A. PATRA and S. K. CHAUDHURI, *Magn. Reson. Chem.*, 1987, **25**, 95.
8. J. N. SHOOLERY, *J. Nat. Prod.*, 1984, **47**, 226, A. E. DÉROME, "Modern NMR Techniques for Chemistry Research", Pergamon, Oxford, 1987.
9. A. BAX and G. A. MORRIS, *J Magn Reson.*, 1981, **42**, 501.
10. A. BAX, R. FREEMAN and T. A. FRIENKEL, *J. Am. Chem Soc*, 1981, **103**, 2102 *J. Magn. Reson.*, 1981, **43**, 478, T. H. MARECI and R. FREEMAN, *J. Magn. Reson.*, 1982, **48**, 158.
11. O. PRAKASH, R. ROY, H. S. GARG and D. S. BHAKUNI, *Magn. Reson. Chem.*, 1987, **25**, 89.